

THE ROLE OF THE "GREAT SILK ROAD" IN THE HISTORY OF UZBEKISTAN AND ITS CONTRIBUTION TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TOURISM INDUSTRY TODAY

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Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada "Buyuk Ipak yo'li" ning Yevroosiyo materiginining turli qismlarini bog'lovchi savdo-sotiq va diplomatik aloqalar maqsadida tashkil qilingan yo'llar tizimi bo'lib shakllangan hamda "Buyuk Ipak yo'li" ning asosiy markazlaridan bo'lib kelgan O'zbekiston Respublikasining Samarqand, Buxoro, Xiva hamda hozirgi Surxondaryo va Toshkent xududlari to'g'ri keladi. Pirovard Buyuk Ipak yo'lining Respublikamiz Turizmida sohasida tutgan o'rni.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Vizantiya imperiyasi, "ipak yo'li", YUNESKO, O'zbekturizm, Iskandar Maqduniy, Jahon sayyohlik tashkiloti.*

Abstract. *In this article, the "Great Silk Road" was formed as a system of roads connecting different parts of the Eurasian continent, organized for trade and diplomatic relations, and it was one of the main centers of the "Great Silk Road". Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva and the present Surkhondaryo and Tashkent regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan correspond. The role of Pirovard in the field of tourism of the Great Silk Road in our Republic.*

Keywords: *Byzantine Empire, Silk Road, UNESCO, Uzbek tourism, Alexander the Great, World Tourism Organization.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье «Великий шелковый путь» формировался как система дорог, соединяющих разные части Евразийского континента, организованных с целью торговых и дипломатических отношений, и являлся одним из главных центров «Великого шелкового пути». Соответствуют Самаркандская, Бухарская, Хивинская и нынешние Сурхандарьинская и Ташкентская области Республики Узбекистан. Роль Пировада в сфере туризма Великого Шелкового пути в нашей республике.*

Ключевые слова: *Византийская империя, Шелковый путь, ЮНЕСКО, узбекский туризм, Александр Македонский, Всемирная туристская организация.*

Introduction

In 1877, the famous German scientist Karl Richthofen published his "China" in a major scientific work, the vast Eurasian continent called the system of roads connecting its parts "Silk Road", later the term "Great Silk Road" was adopted. Between the East and the West until the 2nd century BC. There are connections made through Central Asian caravan routes. It was found in the Poziryk fortress in the Highland Altai, Products made in Asia Minor, Afghanistan, and Central Greek items found in Asia can be an example. Alexander with the structure of the Macedonian kingdom, these relations were established correctly. The Sogdians played an important role in building the eastern part of the "Great Silk Road". who played a role. From Aria to Antiochia in Margiyona (ancient near the city of Bairamali The ruins of the city of Marv) left, then turned to the east, Bactra He went to (the city of Balkh in northern Afghanistan). Way from here headed north, passed Amudarya around Termiz and then It went in 2 directions. The first of the way, Iron along the North through the gate to Morocco (Samarkand), from there to Fergana left, and the second one in the south along the Surkhondaryo valley took him to the mountainous land of the comedians (now Karategin). Har both directions lead to Tashminor. It is some scientists. In the

Tashkent region, others are located in the Oloy Valley they count. In 1987, UNESCO was the UN organization for cultural development within the framework of the international decade "Silk Road Dialogue". accepted the program. This program is a rich culture of the peoples of Central Asia implies a comprehensive study of its history. But its main goal is a stronger cultural relationship between the East and the West and establishing economic ties, living in these great continents from the improvement of mutual relations between a large number of peoples consists of Many (more than 30) international scientific conferences (including Samarkand, October 1990, November 2014; Bukhara, February 1996) and seminars were held. International together along the Great Silk Road expeditions was organized, films were created, books, brochures, and articles were published, and some archaeological and architectural monuments were repaired. In some Eastern countries (India, China, Uzbekistan, Sri Lanka, and Japan) study of the Great Silk Road special scientific institutes have been established. For example, the UN and Central Asia in the city of Samarkand according to the decision of UNESCO International Research Institute was opened. In May 1997 Orta Sarakhs-Mashhad railway connecting Asia with Iran The construction of the section was completed, thus Central Asian countries Persia to the armpit, and European countries to Central Asia they had the opportunity. The main tourist destinations organized in Uzbekistan include the "Great Silk Road" tourist route. In 1994 137 "Silk Road" of the World Tourism Organization in Tashkent and Samarkand an international meeting was held on the development of the project Uzbekistan was designated as the center of this ancient route.

On June 2, 1995, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan opened the "Great Silk Road" to strengthen Uzbekistan's participation in reconstruction and adopted a decree on measures to develop international tourism in the republic. On this basis, "Uzbektourism" from 200 along the historical destinations passed by the national company "Silk Road". Developed more directions. They cover the main tourist areas and Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, and Fergana Valley pass through the cities. Branches of the "Great Silk Road". cities of Andijan, Namangan, Fergana, Termiz, and Nukus route passing through "Golden Ring of Fergana" Kokan, Fergana, It includes the cities of Andijan and Namangan. By now, it can be considered that the foundation for the development of tourism in Uzbekistan has been laid. The proof of this is the adoption by the President of the decree of June 2, 1995 "On increasing the participation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the restoration of the Great Silk Road and developing international tourism in the republic". According to this decree, tourist enterprises received several tax benefits. This decree stimulated the development of tourist destinations in historical and cultural cities located on the "Great Silk Road". For thousands of years, the "Great Silk Road" has been considered an important and effective way to unite the peoples of Asia and Europe. Goods, knowledge, technologies, and cultures were exchanged along the same road, which helped the development of cities and countries. Even now, it is difficult to assess the global significance of this road for mankind. However, even after finishing his career, interest in him did not disappear. In particular, it can be seen that the active participation of transport and information communications, industrial production, trade in goods and services, and the integration processes of Asian and European regions gave the "second breath" of the "Great Silk Road". One form of development of international tourism on the "Great Silk Road" is the formation of a global Trans-Asian transport line connecting Southeast Asia with Europe. It includes Japan, China, India, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Kazakhstan, Caucasus countries, West Asian countries (Pakistan, Iran), and of course European countries. It should be noted that the search for "Dolphin" is part of the TRACEKA. The role and importance of the "Great Silk Road" in the development of international

tourism in Uzbekistan is limitless. For several centuries, the peoples who lived in the West and East of this land were connected by the trade route, which stretched from South-East Asia to the countries of the Mediterranean Sea and was called the "Great Silk Road". was standing. The main reason why this road is called the "Silk Road" is that the main part of the goods transported here are silk fabrics and products. The secrets of silk production have been hidden from other people by Chinese masters for thousands of years. But the products transported on the "Great Silk Road" were not only silk but also bronze, porcelain, wool, raw materials, and products made from them. The "Great Silk Road" has a history of almost two thousand years, and this road mainly went from Italy through Turkey to Iraq and Iran. From there, it passed through Central Asia and North Pamir and reached Kashgar and Yorkent. Here the road split into two and went around the Takla-Makon desert from the north, joined again near Lake Lobnor, and went to China. Since 1994, the World Tourism Organization's "Great Silk Road" has actively promoted the project at all major international fairs: TTV in Berlin, WTM in London, and FJTUR in Madrid. According to the predictions of the World Tourism Organization, by 2020, China will be the main tourist destination in the world. This country currently has 22 mln.

Develop tourism in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions, and Tashkent city in 2023

TARGET INDICATORS

T/r	Name of the area	Plan of visit of foreign tourists in 2023 (thousands)	from that in quarters			
			I quarter	II quarter	III quarter	IV quarter
by republic		10,000	1 487.5	2 332.3	3 150.3	3 029.9
1.	Republic of Karakalpakstan	112	16.7	26.1	35.3	33.9
2.	Andijan region	154	22.9	35.9	48.5	46.7
3.	Bukhara region	1 262	187.7	294.3	397.6	382.3
4.	Jizzakh region	140	20.8	32.7	44.1	42.4
5.	Kashkadarya region	210	31.2	49.0	66.2	63.6
6.	Navoi region	140	20.8	32.7	44.1	42.4
7.	Namangan region	154	22.9	35.9	48.5	46.7
8.	Samarkand region	2 104	313.0	490.7	662.9	637.4
9.	Surkhandarya region	56	8.3	13.1	17.6	17.0
10.	Syrdarya region	56	8.3	13.1	17.6	17.0
11.	Tashkent region	421	62.6	98.2	132.6	127.5
12.	Fergana region	421	62.6	98.2	132.6	127.5
13.	Khorezm region	561	83.5	130.8	176.7	170.0
14.	Tashkent city	4 209	626.2	981.6	1 326.0	1 275.5

It takes sixth place in terms of receiving tourists, and with an average annual growth of 8%, the number of tourists coming to China reached 137 million, and Hong Kong reached 59 million. reaches a person and takes the first place. Based on this, the participants of the "Great Silk Road" project faced the issue of taking into account the countries in the formation of the tourist product, for example, Germany - Uzbekistan - China, France - Uzbekistan - Hong Kong, etc. Annual

expenses of tourists are 5 bln. taking into account the dollar, Uzbekistan also has a sufficient opportunity to form and absorb some part of this currency. Because the majority of tourists traveling to China along the "Great Silk Road" travel through our republic. This means that foreign tourists will receive a certain amount of currency in the state budget for using tourist facilities and vehicles in our country. Therefore, it is necessary to develop and implement transport (transit) routes along the "Great Silk Road" for foreign tourists. In this matter, cultural and educational tourism is of greatest interest. For example, in 2008, 915,000 visitors came to Uzbekistan, 5.6% of them traveled for tourist purposes, 74.4% on private visas, and the remaining 20% traveled for various other purposes. Many visitors were interested in the history, culture, and religious monuments of the country. In October 1994, the Council of the World Tourism Organization was held in Uzbekistan with the participation of the United Nations and its prestigious organization, UNESCO, aiming to restore its place and importance in history and to develop tourism. Council members adopted the Samarkand Declaration aimed at restoring and developing tourism along the Silk Road.

In my conclusion: Based on the information provided, Samarkand is an important historical city located on the Silk Road, and is a popular tourist destination. This has a positive impact on our economy, and there is a growing demand for further study of our rich history. To promote tourism and educate people about the history of the Silk Road modern technologies such as 3D videos and images can be effectively used through online platforms. Organizing events in the Samarkand region can also be a great way to highlight its historical significance.

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